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Some remarks on the questions with interrogative pronouns in Vietnamese textbooks for non-Vietnamese speakers

Abstract. As in other languages, question is one of four types of sentences classified according to purpose of the communication, which is commonly used in Vietnamese. In terms of teaching Vietnamese as a foreign language, questions also play an important role. The research object of this article is *questions with interrogative pronouns* in Vietnamese textbooks for non-Vietnamese speakers at elementary and intermediate levels. Based on the survey results, the purpose of our research is to offer suggestions and comments on the inclusion and use of this type of question in Vietnamese textbooks for non-Vietnamese speakers at elementary and intermediate levels as well as provide recommendations on the teaching and compilation of Vietnamese textbooks. Major research methods are the description, comparison and other statistical and classification methods. Research materials are questions in the conversation sections of 10 Vietnamese textbooks for non-Vietnamese speakers at elementary and intermediate levels. The outline of this research is as follows: 1. Introduction. 2. Questions and questions with interrogative pronouns in Vietnamese. 3. Survey on the use of questions with interrogative pronouns in Vietnamese textbooks at elementary and intermediate levels. 4. Survey on the distribution of questions with interrogative pronouns in Vietnamese textbooks at elementary and intermediate levels.

Key words: questions, questions with interrogative pronouns, Vietnamese textbooks for non-Vietnamese speakers.

Introduction. Reason to select the topic. Question is one of four types of sentences classified according to purpose of the announcement, which is commonly used in communication. Of which questions with interrogative pronouns are the most commonly used type in conversational structures.

There are many researches regarding questions; however, up to now, there have been no researches on the type of questions with interrogative pronouns in Vietnamese textbooks for non-Vietnamese speakers as a second language.

Due to the increasing demand of learning Vietnamese, the study of questions with interrogative pronouns in Vietnamese textbooks will be helpful in teaching and learning Vietnamese; supporting the compilation of Vietnamese textbooks for non-Vietnamese speakers at different levels.

For the reasons as mentioned above, we have selected the topic titled “Some com-

ments on data of questions with interrogative pronouns in Vietnamese textbooks for non-Vietnamese speakers at elementary and intermediate levels” in this research.

Purposes and tasks of the research

Research purposes:

- To clarify concepts about questions, questions with interrogative pronouns, and classification of questions in Vietnamese.

- To survey sub-categories of questions with interrogative pronouns in three sets of Vietnamese textbooks for non-Vietnamese speakers at elementary and intermediate levels in order to have an overview of the inclusion and use of this type of question in the textbooks. Thereby, we offer suggestions and comments for teaching and learning, as well as the compilation of Vietnamese textbooks for non-Vietnamese speakers at elementary and intermediate levels.

Tasks:

- To learn about the research situation and establish a theoretical basis of questions and questions with interrogative pronouns;

- To make statistics of the quantity and classification of types of questions with interrogative pronouns in Vietnamese textbooks for non-Vietnamese speakers at elementary and intermediate levels.

- To offer suggestions, comments and proposals on the inclusion and use of questions with interrogative pronouns in Vietnamese textbooks for non-Vietnamese speakers.

Research data and methods

Research data: We have conducted a survey of questions with interrogative pronouns in the conversation sections of three sets of Vietnamese textbooks for non-Vietnamese speakers at elementary and intermediate levels. We selected 10 Vietnamese textbooks for non-Vietnamese speakers. Based on the titles of such textbooks, these books are arranged according to the level as follows:

Table 1.

Elementary level	
GT1 – A1	<i>Giáo trình tiếng Việt cơ sở (Elementary Vietnamese)</i> , Volume 1, Nguyen Viet Huong, National University Publishing House, 2017.
GT2 – A2	<i>Giáo trình tiếng Việt cơ sở (Elementary Vietnamese)</i> , Volume 2, Nguyen Viet Huong, National University Publishing House, 2017.
GT3 - A1	<i>Giáo trình tiếng Việt trình độ A (Vietnamese A)</i> , Volume 1, Doan Thien Thuat (Editor-in-chief), World Publishing House, 2006.
GT4 – A2	<i>Giáo trình tiếng Việt trình độ A (Vietnamese A)</i> , Volume 2, Doan Thien Thuat (Editor-in-chief), World Publishing House, 2006.
GT5 - A1	<i>Giáo trình tiếng Việt cho người nước ngoài VSL1 (Vietnamese for Foreigners VSL1)</i> , Nguyen Van Hue (Editor-in-chief), Educational Publishing House, 2004.
GT6 – A2	<i>Giáo trình tiếng Việt cho người nước ngoài VSL2 (Vietnamese for Foreigners VSL2)</i> , Nguyen Van Hue (Editor-in-chief), HCMC University of Education Publishing House, 2008
Intermediate level	
GT7 – B	<i>Giáo trình tiếng Việt nâng cao (Intermediate Vietnamese)</i> , Volume 1, Nguyen Viet Huong, National University Publishing House, 2017.
GT8 - B	<i>Giáo trình thực hành tiếng Việt trình độ B (Practice Vietnamese - Level B)</i> , Doan Thien Thuat (Editor-in-chief), World Publishing House, 2007.
GT9 – B1	<i>Giáo trình tiếng Việt cho người nước ngoài VSL3 (Vietnamese for Foreigners VSL3)</i> , Nguyen Van Hue (Editor-in-chief), Educational Publishing House, 2004.
GT10 – B2	<i>Giáo trình tiếng Việt cho người nước ngoài VSL4 (Vietnamese for Foreigners VSL4)</i> , Nguyen Van Hue (Editor-in-chief), Educational Publishing House, 2004.

Research methods:

Two methods are used in this research including the descriptive method and comparative method. In addition, we also use statistical and classification methods in this research.

Questions and questions with interrogative pronouns in Vietnamese

Concept of questions

The dictionary of linguistic terms by Nhu Y explains the question as “a sentence indicating a question and punctuated at the end with a question mark (?) in the written form. Means of expressing interrogative sentences are question intonation (emphasis on

the word you want to ask), interrogative words (when, where, what, why etc.), and word orders". [9. p. 39].

Linguists study questions in both structural and functional directions.

In terms of structural direction, the authors consider the question as one of four types of sentences classified according to purpose of the announcement but identified according to the formal criteria. Typical trends are Bui Duc Tinh (1952), Nguyen Kim Than (1964), Ho Le (1979), Hoang Trong Phien (1980), Diep Quang Ban (1989) Nguyen Kim Than stated that "*the purpose of ordinary questions is to raise the speaker's skepticism and generally require the listener to report on the object or its characteristics*" [8, p. 599]. He said that legitimate questions are "*those that really aim to raise the speaker's skepticism and require a response from the listener (only in the exceptional case of a monologue, the response is not required)*" [8, p. 600]. Diep Quang Ban (1989) claimed that "*Questions are often used to raise unknown or doubtful things and wait for answers and explanations from the listener, and in terms of form, questions also have certain characteristic signs*" [3, p. 247].

Regarding the functional direction, the question is considered as the typical expression form of the act of asking as the speech act. Cao Xuan Hao (1991) said that "*Interrogative sentences (questions) of Vietnamese as well as of many other languages, in addition to the value of asking (notification request) as its direct illocutionary value, it may have derivative illocutionary value(s) (such as negation, affirmation, doubt, challenge or argument)*" [2, p. 390]. Based on the concept of illocutionary value, he conceived of legitimate questions as "*Those are questions that require an answer informing a fact or a certain argument of a fact that is presupposed to be true*" [2, p. 391] and other questions with illocutionary values "*When a sentence is in the form of a question (to some extent), but there is no request to provide a notice corresponding with the content of that question, its illocutionary values change and become another speech act. J.Searle (1979) calls it as an indi-*

rect speech act" [2, p. 400]. In the textbook named "*Basic Linguistics and Vietnamese*", Bui Tat Tuom, Nguyen Van Bang, and Hoang Xuan Tam (1997) said that "*An interrogative sentence is a question with illocutionary forces that require an answer informing a situation or part of a situation that is presupposed to be true*" [1, p. 288].

Types of questions in Vietnamese

Vietnamese linguists classify questions in two directions as follows: The first one is to classify questions according to its structures (expression form) and the second one is to classify questions according to its contents (functions).

For the first direction, typical authors are Nguyen Kim Than (1964), Hoang Trong Phien (1980), Diep Quang Ban (1989) and Nguyen Phu Phong etc. Nguyen Kim Than (1964) based on natures and methods of expression to classify interrogative sentences. He classified interrogative sentences into the following types: *Legitimate questions* (including sub-categories such as Open-ended questions, Limited questions, Multiple-choice questions, Emphasis questions), *Rhetorical questions*, *Interrogative - Negative questions*, *Interrogative - Affirmative questions*, and *Interrogative - Imperative questions*. Based on the methods of expression, Nguyen Kim Than classified questions into sub-categories consisting of: *Questions with interrogative pronouns (who, what etc.)*, *questions with conjunctions (or, nor)*, *questions with final particles (oh, huh etc.)*. Actually, his classification is still based on the form of expression. Hoang Trong Phien (1980) also based on the sentence structures to classify questions into *blank questions or simple questions* (using specialized words to ask like *who, what, how* etc.) and *multiple-choice questions* [see 6]. Diep Quang Ban (1989) based on the form of expression to divide questions into the following sub-categories: *Questions with interrogative pronouns* (using different pronouns such as *who, what, when, how, how much, how long, why* etc.), *questions with adjuncts* (using adjuncts such as *do... don't you, is it (or isn't it ...? Have/has already... yet?)*), *questions with conjunction words "or"*, *questions with*

specialized particles (using particles such as *oh, huh, hmm, ouch, wow* etc.). Nguyen Phu Phong classified questions into *Indefinite questions or open-ended questions* (posed with indefinite elements such as “*where*”, “*why*”, “*what*” etc.), *transitional or closed questions* (means of expression such as intonation, lexical elements like *or, do you...don't you, already...yet, either...or, neither...nor*), *Directional questions* (interrogative means are particles at the end of the sentence such as *ah, huh, hum* etc.).

In terms of the second direction, questions are classified on the basis of its contents (functions). The typical author is Cao Xuan Hao (1991), he based on the illocutionary force to classify questions as follows: *Legitimate questions* (special questions starting with *wh*-words, General questions, Limited questions, Meta-linguistic questions, questions ended with “*don't you*” and “*isn't it*”). *Illegitimate questions* (including subcategories such as imperative questions, affirmative questions, negative questions, conjecture, uncertain or confused questions, and exclamation questions). At this point, linguists have studied questions from functional perspectives, interested in their activities in the communication, not only from the perspective of pure, static and formal structures. In addition to questions requiring information, which some authors call as the legitimate question, there is also a type of question that does not require providing information, which is called as illegitimate questions, rhetorical questions. Dinh Trong Lac (1994) stated that rhetorical questions “*are in the form of not requiring answers but only increasing the expressiveness of utterances*” [see 5]. In addition, Diep Quang Ban said that rhetorical questions “*are questions that do not need answers*” [see 3]. Questions of this type are in the form of questions but do not ask for answers. According to Le Dong (1985), based on the question-answer relationship, questions are distinguished as follows [see 7]:

- Legitimate answer: Exact answer for the enquiry point, meeting additional de-

mands of missing information of the questioner.

- Answer: Fail to meet the information demands of the question and completely go beyond the enquiry point.

All above are methods of classifying Vietnamese questions by the authors according to two trends. In this research, we only survey one sub-category of the legitimate question: that is the questions with interrogative pronouns in Vietnamese.

Questions with interrogative pronouns in Vietnamese

We use the concept of question classification by Diep Quang Ban, which is based on the form of expression to classify questions. Specifically, legitimate questions will be classified into the following sub-categories:

• *Question with adjuncts*: This type of questions often uses pairs of adjuncts to form question frames as follows:

- *Do ... don't you? (or have you?)*

- *Isn't it? (or is it?)*

- *Have/has already... yet?*

- *... done (or already)... yet? (or ... done yet?)*

• *Questions with interrogative pronouns*: This type of question often uses interrogative pronouns such as *who, when, where, how, why, how long* etc.

• *Multiple-choice question*: This type of question is formed from the use of the choice word *or, either*.

• *Questions using specialized particles*: This type of question often uses specialized particles such as *oh, huh, hmm, yeah* etc.

According to the opinions of Diep Quang Ban, questions with interrogative pronouns are used to ask about certain points in a sentence; the enquiry point is the point containing interrogative pronouns. This type of sentence can be called as an interrogative sentence with certain enquiry point [4, p. 276]:

• Type 1: Ask about people, things, including interrogative pronouns like *who, what, which*.

For example: Người bán (*Seller*): Anh mua gì ạ? (*What do you want to buy?*)

Người mua (Buyer): Tôi muốn mua một chiếc đồng hồ đeo tay. (I want to buy a wristwatch.) [GT2-A2, page 81]

•Type 2: Ask about quantity and order, interrogative pronouns are used like *how much, how many*.

For example: *Cô giáo (Teacher): Quyển từ điển ấy có bao nhiêu trang? (How many pages does that dictionary have?)*

Nga: Dạ 100 trang ạ. (100 pages). [GT1-A1, page 161]

•Type 3: Ask about the time, interrogative pronouns are used like *when, how long, which time*.

For example: *Lien: Thẻ em định đi bao lâu?(How long will you go?)*

Mai: Chỉ 2 ngày thôi ạ. (Just 2 days) [GT2-A2, page 213]

•Type 4: Ask about the place, interrogative pronouns are used like *where, what place*.

For example: *Mary: Bây giờ anh sống ở đâu? (Where do you live now?)*

Huy: Chúng tôi vẫn sống ở Bách Khoa. (We still live in Bach Khoa) [GT2-A2, page 188]

•Type 5: Ask about manners and natures, interrogative pronouns are used like *how*.

For example: *Tom: Anh thấy Hà Nội thế nào?(How do you feel about Hanoi City?)*

Dung:Đẹp lắm. (It is very beautiful) [GT6-A2, page 39]

•Type 6: Ask about the reason, interrogative pronouns are used like *why, for what*.

For example: *A: Mấy hôm nay sao anh không đi học? (Why don't you do to school these days?)*

B: Thầy giáo vừa nói dài vừa nói dở. Chán lắm. (The lecturer teaches so long and so boring. I'm bored.) [GT9-B1, page 148]

Below we will survey the data of questions with interrogative pronouns in Vietnamese textbooks for non-Vietnamese speakers at elementary and intermediate levels.

Survey on the use of questions with interrogative pronouns in Vietnamese textbooks for non-Vietnamese speakers at elementary and intermediate levels

Situation of questions with interrogative pronouns in the conversation sections of Vietnamese textbooks at the elementary and intermediate textbooks

Survey data at the elementary textbooks

After finishing the survey, results are as follows:

Table 2. Rate of questions with interrogative pronouns in 03 sets of textbooks at the elementary level.

No.	Textbook	Quantity	Rate (%)
1	GT1-A1	35	9.4
2	GT2-A2	92	24.7
3	GT3-A1	26	7
4	GT4-A2	38	10.2
5	GT5-A1	101	27.2
6	GT6-A2	80	21.5
Total		372	100

According to the statistical results, the textbooks all use questions with interrogative pronouns with different quantities. Of which, according to each textbook, GT5-A1 uses the highest quantity of questions with interrogative pronouns (accounting for 27.2%). The following is GT2-A2 (24.7%) and GT6-A2 (21.5%). GT3-A1 uses this type of question at the lowest rate (just accounting for 7%).

Based on 03 sets of textbooks, the *Vietnamese for Foreigners VSL 1,2* uses the highest quantity of questions with interrogative pronouns. The next textbook is *Elementary Vietnamese* (Volume 1 and 2). The *Vietnamese A* textbook (Volume 1 and 2) uses the lowest quantity of this question type.

Survey results at the intermediate level

Table 3. Rate of questions with interrogative pronouns in 03 sets of textbooks at the intermediate level.

No.	Textbook	Quantity	Rate (%)
1	GT7-B	51	30
2	GT8-B	30	17.6
3	GT9-B1	43	25.3
4	GT10-B2	46	27.1
Total		170	100

According to the statistical results, the GT7-B uses the highest quantity of questions with interrogative pronouns (accounting for 30%). The following is textbooks GT10-B2 (27.1%) and GT9-B1 (25.3%). GT8-B uses the lowest quantity of questions with interrogative pronouns (accounting for 17.6%). For 03 sets of intermediate textbooks, the *Vietnamese for Foreigners VSL (3, 4)* uses the highest quantity of questions with interrogative pronouns; followed by the *Intermediate Vietnamese* and *Practice Vietnamese - Level B*.

Comparison of the two levels

On the basis of the survey results on using questions with interrogative pronouns in 03 sets of textbooks at both elementary and

intermediate levels, we found that each textbook uses a different quantity of questions with interrogative pronouns. At the elementary level, the quantity of questions with interrogative pronouns used in the conversation section is high (372 votes). And at the intermediate level, the quantity of this type of question is lower (170 votes).

Situation of the use of different types of questions with interrogative pronouns in elementary and intermediate textbooks

As mentioned in the theory part, questions with interrogative pronouns include 6 types of questions. We will survey 6 types of questions in 03 sets of elementary textbooks and 03 sets of intermediate textbooks.

Survey results at the elementary level

Table 4. Types of questions with interrogative pronouns used in Vietnamese textbooks for non-Vietnamese speakers at the elementary level.

Textbook	Type 1	Type 2	Type 3	Type 4	Type 5	Type 6	Total
GT1-A1	20	6	0	6	3	0	35
GT2-A2	26	27	7	18	9	5	92
GT3-A1	9	4	2	5	5	1	26
GT4-A2	19	6	1	5	3	4	38
GT5-A1	45	31	8	16	0	1	101
GT6-A2	35	16	6	7	12	4	80
Total	154	90	24	57	32	15	372

The survey results showed that the inclusion of questions with interrogative pronouns in the conversation sections is not the same; there is a high different number of this question type. The Type-1 question is used at the highest rate (154 votes). The following are Type 2, Type 4, Type 5, and Type 6. Type 3

is used at the lowest rate among 6 types of questions. Of which, Type 1 is tended to be used at the highest rate in all 3 sets of textbooks at the elementary level, then followed by Type 2 and Type 4.

Survey results at the intermediate level

Table 5: Types of questions with interrogative pronouns used in Vietnamese textbooks for non-Vietnamese speakers at the intermediate level.

Textbook	Type 1	Type 2	Type 3	Type 4	Type 5	Type 6	Total
GT7-B	11	11	9	3	14	2	51
GT8-B	12	3	2	5	8	0	30
GT9-B1	17	3	0	8	4	11	43
GT10-B2	14	3	3	8	5	13	46
Total	54	20	14	24	31	26	170

According to the survey results, Type 1 is the most used of all. Then followed by Type 5, Type 6, Type 4, Type 2, and Type 3. Each set of textbooks uses a different number of question types. GT7-B uses Type 5 at the highest rate, and then followed by Type 1, 2, 3, 5 and 6. GT8-B tends to use Type 1 at the highest frequency, then followed by Type 4, 2, 3, and 6. Meanwhile, Type 1 is used in GT9-B1 and GT10-B2 at the highest rate, then followed by Type 6, 4, 5, 2, and 3, respectively.

Comparison of the 2 levels

Based on the survey results, the number of questions with interrogative pronouns included in the conversation sections at the elementary level is higher than that of the intermediate level. At the elementary level, Types 1, 2, and 4 are most commonly used ones; Types 3, 5, and 6 are used at a lower rate with a big difference among types of sentences. At the intermediate level, Type 1, 5, and 6 are most commonly used; then followed by Types 4, 2, and 3, respectively; and there

is no big difference among types of sentences at the intermediate level

Survey on the distribution of questions with interrogative pronouns in Vietnamese textbooks for non-Vietnamese speakers at elementary and intermediate levels

Distribution of questions with interrogative pronouns according to lesson structures of the textbooks

Survey results at the elementary level

In the textbooks, the authors present different layouts; however, the lesson layout mainly consists of the following sections: Conversations, Vocabulary, Grammar Notes, Practices (speaking practice, listening practice, and writing practice), Readings, and Exercises. We conduct a survey of questions with interrogative pronouns in the layout of textbooks on the basis of the following parts: Conversation – Grammar Notes – Practices – Readings – Exercises. Survey results are as follows:

Table 6. Quantity of questions with interrogative pronouns distributed in lesson structures at the elementary level.

Textbook	Lesson structure					Total	Rate (%)
	Conversation	Grammar note	Practice	Reading	Exercise		
GT1-A1	31	40	315	0	87	473	20.3
GT2-A2	72	51	551	0	86	760	32.5
GT3-A1	28	2	140	8	52	230	9.8
GT4-A2	31	2	108	0	30	171	7.3
GT5-A1	110	34	136	0	103	383	16.4
GT6-A2	85	6	192	0	37	320	13.7
Total	357	135	1442	8	395	2337	

According to the survey results, the number of questions with interrogative pronouns included in the textbook at the elementary level is different and there is also a big difference among the textbooks. Specifically, the *Elementary Vietnamese* textbook series (GT1-A1, GT2-A2) uses questions with interrogative pronouns at the highest rate in lesson structures (52.5%). Then followed by the *Vietnamese for Foreigners VSL* (GT5-A1, GT6-A2), accounting for 30.1%. The *Vietnamese A*

textbook (GT3-A1, GT4-A2) uses questions with interrogative pronouns at the lowest rate compared to the two textbooks as mentioned above (accounting for 17.1%).

In which, this type of question is used the most in the Practice sections (1442 votes), then followed by Exercises (395 votes), Conversations (357 votes), Grammar Notes (135 votes), and Readings (8 votes).

Survey results at the intermediate level

Table 7. Quantity of questions with interrogative pronouns distributed in lesson structures at the intermediate level.

No.	Textbook	Lesson structure					Total	Rate (%)
		Conversation	Grammar note	Practice	Reading	Exercise		
1	GT7-B	43	11	332	0	12	398	45.7
2	GT8-B	21	2	19	13	106	161	18.5
3	GT9-B1	35	0	104	0	5	144	16.6
4	GT10-B2	38	2	103	0	24	167	19.2
	Total	137	15	558	13	147	870	

According to the survey results, the number of questions with interrogative pronouns included in the lesson structures of textbooks at the intermediate level is different and there is a big difference among the textbooks. Among the 3 sets of intermediate textbooks, the *Intermediate Vietnamese* textbook (GT7-B) uses the highest rate of questions with interrogative pronouns (45.7%), the *Vietnamese for Foreigners* textbook (GT9-B1, GT10-B2) uses the questions with interrogative pronouns at the second rate (accounting for 35.8%), and the *Practice Vietnamese - Level B* (GT8-B) uses the questions with interrogative pronouns at the lowest level compared with 3 sets of textbooks (18.5%).

In which, this type of question is used the most in the Practice sections (558 votes), then followed by Exercises (147 votes), Conversations (137 votes), Grammar Notes (15 votes), and Readings (13 votes).

Comparison of the two levels

The survey results showed that the number of questions with interrogative pronouns included in the lesson structures is much higher at the elementary level than that of the intermediate level. However, at both levels, the number of questions with interrogative pronouns included in the lesson structures has the same trend. That is this type of question is used at the highest rate in the Practice section, then the following are Exercises, Conversations, Grammar Notes, and Readings.

Distribution of types of questions with interrogative pronouns according to lesson structures of textbooks

Survey results at the elementary level

Six types of questions with interrogative pronouns in the lesson structures of textbooks are surveyed. Results are as follows:

Table 8. Number of types of questions with interrogative pronouns in lesson structures at the elementary level.

Textbook	Type 1	Type 2	Type 3	Type 4	Type 5	Type 6	Total
GT1-A1	211	86	0	36	140	0	473
GT2-A2	241	216	146	71	36	50	760
GT3-A1	123	45	12	24	22	5	230
GT4-A2	83	18	12	23	20	15	171
GT5-A1	135	105	53	68	7	15	383
GT6-A2	125	68	22	38	44	23	320
Total	918	538	245	260	269	108	2337

According to the survey results, the number of each type of question included in lesson structures of the elementary textbooks is quite high. Specifically, Type 1 is used the most in lesson structures (918 votes), then followed by Type 2 (538 votes), Type 5 (269 votes), Type 4 (260 votes), Type 3 (245 votes), and Type 6 (108 votes). These are el-

ementary textbooks; therefore, question types often use interrogative pronouns such as *what*, *who*, *how much*, and *how* at the highest rate. Meanwhile, the type of questions using interrogative pronouns such as *why*, *what* is rarely used in these textbooks.

Survey results at the intermediate level

Table 9. Number of types of questions with interrogative pronouns in lesson structures at the intermediate level.

Textbook	Type 1	Type 2	Type 3	Type 4	Type 5	Type 6	Total
GT7-B	156	69	64	41	51	17	398
GT8-B	68	15	6	20	28	24	161
GT9-B1	49	13	6	17	16	43	144
GT10-B2	72	16	9	17	12	41	167
Total	345	113	85	95	107	125	870

Based on the survey results, the number of questions with interrogative pronouns included in the lesson structures is lower than that of the elementary level. In which, Type 1 is used at the highest one among 6 types of questions (345 votes), then followed by Type 6 (125 votes), Type 2 (113 votes), Type 5 (107 votes), Type 4 (95 votes), and Type 3 (85 votes). At the intermediate level, learners' Vietnamese proficiency has been improved, so questions of Type 5 and 6 are used at a higher frequency.

Comparison of the two levels

We found out that at the elementary level, Types 1, 2, and 5 are used a lot in the lesson structures. Types 3, 4, and 6 are used at a lower rate. In which, the *Elementary Vietnamese* textbook (GT1-A1, GT2-A2) and *Vietnamese for Foreigners* textbook VSL 1, 2

(GT5-A1, GT6-A2) often use Types 1, 2, and 5 at a higher frequency compared to Types 3, 4, and 6. The *Vietnamese A* (GT3-A1, GT4-A2) often uses Type 1, 2, and 4, and Types 3, 5, and 6 are used less often. At the intermediate level, there is a change when Types 1, 6, and 2 are used a lot, while Types 5, 4, and 3 are used less often. Meanwhile, the *Intermediate Vietnamese* textbook (GT7-B) uses Types 1, 2, and 3 more often than Types 4, 5, and 6. The *Practice Vietnamese - Level B* textbook uses Types 1, 5, and 6 at a higher frequency than Types 4, 2, and 3. The *Vietnamese for Foreigners VSL 3, 4* (GT9-B1, GT10-B2) uses Types 1, 6, and 4 more often than Types 2, 5, and 3.

Conclusion

Based on the survey of the use of questions with interrogative pronouns in 3 sets of

textbooks at the two levels, we found that this type of question is used a lot.

- At the elementary level, the number of this type of questions is used at a higher rate compared to the intermediate level; in which, the *Vietnamese for Foreigners VSL 1, 2* uses questions with interrogative pronouns at the highest rate. Then the *Elementary Vietnamese* textbooks, Volume 1 and 2, come after. The *Vietnamese A* textbooks, Volume 1, 2 ranked the 3rd place. This is the same at the intermediate level.

- In terms of each sub-category: At the elementary level, questions with interrogative pronouns of Types 1, 2, and 4 are used a lot in textbooks. Types 3, 5, and 6 are used less often. At the intermediate level, questions with interrogative pronouns of Types 1, 5, and 6 are used a lot in these textbooks. Types 4, 2, and 3 are used at a lower rate. This difference is due to different levels of learners.

- Regarding the distribution of questions with interrogative pronouns in the lesson structures: In both elementary and intermediate levels, this type of question is distributed at the highest rate in the Practices section, then followed by the Exercises and Conversations. The type of questions is distributed at a very low rate in the Grammar Notes such as GT3-A1 (2 votes), GT4-A2 (2 votes), GT10-B2 (2 votes). Even in some textbooks such as GT9-B1, the Grammar of these sub-categories is not explained. We found that these textbooks have included and used many of these

types of questions in the Conversation, Exercises, and Practice sections, but not in the Grammar Notes section. This will cause difficulties for learners because they are just beginners. We recommend that the authors should fully include question structures with interrogative pronouns in the Grammar Notes so that learners can understand intensively this type of question. Thereby, they can use this type of question proficiently in their communication.

- For the distribution of types of questions with interrogative pronouns in the lesson structures: Due to different levels, Types 1, 2, and 5 are used a lot at the elementary level. Meanwhile, Types 3, 4, and 6 are used at a lower rate. However, we realized that there is a big difference among the types of questions. For example, Type 1 has 918 votes while Type 6 has only 108 votes. Even in the GT1-A1 textbook, Types 3 and 6 are not used in the lesson structures. At the intermediate level, textbooks use all six types of questions. However, the number of question types is lower than that at the elementary level. Types 1, 2, and 6 are used at a higher frequency compared to Types 3, 4, and 5. We found that this is inappropriate at the intermediate level. Because at this level, learners already have a basic foundation of Vietnamese from the elementary level, so the difficulty of these question types should be raised. It means that Types 3, 4, and 5 should be used more frequently than Types 1 and 2.

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